

**THE QUALITATIVE STUDY OF TALENT MANAGEMENT
PROGRAM AT *BADAN PENYELENGGARA JAMINAN
SOSIAL KETENAGAKERJAAN***

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to analyze the implementation and the constraints in the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 talent management program and to construct a roadmap for developing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program in supporting organizational success. By using descriptive qualitative research, data collection is done through interviews and documentation studies for further data processing and data analysis. The first analysis results show that the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 produced unsupportive and supportive impacts of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. Impacts that did not support the successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 were the process of structural change required the process of transformation of employees into human capital, talent mapping for each position had not been fully carried out, and the quite amount of time and process to build optimal personnel talents. The results of the second analysis showed that the constraints in the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program from 2014 to 2018 consisted of constraints with large obstacles or constraints with small obstacles. Constraints with large obstacles to achieve successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 included the process of cultural change that required the support of all employees, the process of transforming employees into human capital, and a quite amount of time and process to build optimal personnel talent. The results of the third

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analysis showed that the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program was the result of an analysis of the conditions for the implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 as a basis and priority issue consideration, also and weighting the rank of the problem on the management implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018.

Keywords: qualitative study, talent management, program implementation, development roadmap

1. Introduction

The development of talent management program is carried out in the context of human resources management within a human capital management frame. Through the development of appropriate talent management programs and in accordance of their needs, companies and employees will get optimal benefits. On a broader scope, talent management means how a company manages its human resources starting from the recruitment process, employee placement, performance appraisal, training and career development, until the employee leaves the company so that ultimately company goals can be achieved (Lewis & Heckman, 2006).

In the Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial Ketenagakerjaan (BPJS Ketenagakerjaan) organization, the talent management program run by the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan is relatively new because the new talent management program is included in the Second Amendment of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan's Strategic Plan 2014-2018. Since it was rolled out as a work program in the Human Capital Division of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, the talent management program has not been recorded in the form of a written report to see its impact on the human resources development program at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan.

Because the talent management program run by BPJS Ketenagakerjaan is relatively new and the talent management program has been briefly included in the Second Amendment of the 2014-2018 BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Strategic Plan, it is necessary to know the conditions of implementing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 will be able to detect constraints in implementation as a condition that does not support the successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

To implement the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program in the future, it is necessary to have a roadmap for developing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program as a specific BPJS Ketenagakerjaan plan for the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program. By making the conditions of implementation and constraints in the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 as an initial basis, the roadmap

for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management programs can be mapped as a specific BPJS Ketenagakerjaan plan.

Thus, the formulation of the problems regarding the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program are:

- a. How is the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018?
- b. What are the constraints in the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018?
- c. What is the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program in supporting its organizational success?

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1 Human Capital

Basically, the concept of human capital is based on the fact that a person (worker) with all his knowledge, experience, education, personality, and behavioral habits is a resource and creates value for the organization. This is because the concept of human capital assumes that skills, knowledge, and similar attributes affect a person's ability to do productive work (Schultz, 1961).

Human capital is a concept that explains that people in organizations and businesses are important assets, have a contribution to development and growth just as physical assets such as machinery and working capital. Human attitudes, skills, and abilities contribute to the organization's performance and productivity. Expenditures for training, development, health and support are investments and those are not just costs but investment indeed (Stockey, 2003).

2.2 Talent Management

Talent management is a way to effectively manage talent in the organization, planning and developing succession in the company, the realization of employee self-development to the fullest, and the optimal use of talent (Rampersad, 2006: 234). Talent management is a process to ensure a company fills key positions for future leaders and positions that support the company's core competencies (unique skills and high strategic value) (Pella & Inayati: 2011: 82). Talent management is the arrangement of organizational human resources processes that are designed to attract, develop, motivate, and retain productive and engaged workers (Ford *et al.*, 2010).

Thus, talent is something that is owned by employees that are built and fostered through training and development programs by an organization for a long-term process that can improve its performance so that it can be a driving force behind their contribution to organizational success. The objectives of talent management include:

- 1) Develop a superior team that is the best in competitive business conditions.
- 2) Obtain replacement candidates for key executive positions.

- 3) Allows for mutual filling between executives from various functional, geographical backgrounds, and business, so they can develop innovation and make the best use of internal resources in the company (Smilansky: 2008: 73)

The benefits of the talent management program are the continuous availability of employees who reach their best potential, able to develop a public reputation for being a good place to work, while fostering the loyalty of employees who have worked in the company (Pella and Inayati: 2011: 87). The talent management dimensions are:

- 1) Inclusion: a situation where individuals feel part of the organizational process.
- 2) Engagement: the relationship between the organization and employees. The engagement process in this talent management model is to ensure that employees are enthusiastic about their work and take positive steps to enhance the organization's reputation.
- 3) Competencies: ensuring employees have the right competencies to work within the organization and fulfill their objectives.
- 4) Retention: ensuring employees remain in the organization and do not move to other companies.

3. Research Methodology

The research method used is a qualitative research method that tends to be descriptive, naturalistic, and related to the "qualitative nature of the data". (Irawan, 2011: 5), and conducted to find out the value of the independent variable, either one or more variables (independent) without making comparisons, or connecting one variable with another variable (Sugiyono, 2013: 11). The research procedure is done with preparation of research proposals, data collection, data coding, data analysis and conclusion drawing. The research informants were determined through purposive sampling techniques.

Data collection techniques are carried out by collecting primary data directly from key informants with interview methods and collecting secondary data directly from documents relating to BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management. For the reliability test, the intercoder reliability test was used. Followed by data analysis using research procedures that produce descriptive data, the use of the Urgency, Seriousness, and Growth Matrices are to determine the priority of the problem and determine the weight of the problem based on the ratio of the amount of data and the number of informants used to determine the priority order of the problem.

4. Research Results and Discussion

4.1 The Implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Talent Management Program 2014-2018

The implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 was detected by deepening the topic of human resources management related to the

talent management program, which consisted of structural changes and organizational culture changes, reasons for using human capital, the use of the term talent management, recruitment processes in context talent management, human resources status in recruitment, human resources training and development processes, human resources training and development targets, human resources placement processes in the context of talent management, talent pool implementation activities, recruitment assessment process results and training in human resources placement, recruitment systems human resources, as well as the human resources retirement preparation program.

Based on the data collected, an intercoder reliability test was performed which resulted in a reliability value of 83% or > 75%, so that the data used had an adequate reliability value. Furthermore, by using the data that has been collected, priorities and the rank of the problems based on its load are obtained in the implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 as follows:

Table 4.1: Problem Priority and Problem Weight Rating Implementation of Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018

No.	Coding Topics	Priority Score			Priority Problem	Load of the Problem Rank
		Urgency	Seriousness	Growth		
1	Structural changes and organizational culture changes	5	4	3	Problem that is very urgent, serious and important enough to be developed	I
2	Reasons for using human capital	3	4	4	Problem that is quite urgent, serious and important to be developed.	VI
3	The use of the term talent management	3	2	3	Problem that is quite urgent, less serious and important enough to be developed	II
4	Recruitment process in the context of talent management	3	3	3	Problem that is quite urgent, quite serious and important enough to be developed	VII
5	The human resources status in recruitment	4	3	3	An urgent problem, quite serious and important enough to be developed	X
6	The human resources training and development process	4	4	3	Problem that is urgent, serious and important enough to be developed	VIII

7	The human resources training and development targets	4	3	2	Problem that is urgent, serious and less important to be developed	III
8	The human resources placement process in the context of talent management	3	3	2	Problem that is quite urgent, quite serious and less important to be developed	IX
9	Implementation of talent pool activities	3	2	3	Problem that is quite urgent, less serious and important enough to be developed	XI
10	Process of assessment on recruitment results and training in human resources placement	3	2	3	Problem that is quite urgent, less serious and important enough to be developed	IV
11	Human resources recruitment systems	5	4	4	A very urgent problem, serious and important issue to be developed	V
12	The human resources retirement preparation program.	4	3	3	An urgent problem, serious enough and important enough to be developed	XII

Based on data collected and reduced, the results of the research on the conditions for the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018, are as follows:

Table 4.2: Research Result - The Condition for the Implementation of Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018

No	Coding Topics	The Condition for the Implementation of Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018
1	Structural changes and organizational culture changes	Changes in organizational structure due to the transformation of the law, service excellence oriented, changes in the business environment
		Changes in organizational culture are still in process, requiring changes in profile competency, changing cultural values at work
		The process of culture change requires the support of all employees, requiring the acceleration of the process in accordance with the intended milestone.
		The process of structural change requires initiation through strategic planning, is expected to increase the number of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, change the Board of Commissioners to the Supervisory Board.
		The process of structural change requires the process of transforming employees into human capital

2	Reasons for using human capital	The difference in the sense of value of human resources as human capital is in line with the principle of organizational transformation to carry out all business processes
		Human capital is expected to contribute greatly to the achievement of organizational goals and organizational success
		The change in direction of HR management has become a holistic HR development for use as sources and organizational tools
		The importance of the capitalization of human resources to remain productive in carrying out the vision and mission of the organization
3	The use of the term talent management	Talents managed through talent management will be optimal for self-development as an organization executive
		Talent becomes a necessity through proper planning and process
		The preparation of high potential employees through professional hire will work sincerely, productively and contributively to produce performance in accordance with their talents
		Building, managing and developing personnel talents is the duty of all elements of the leadership
4	Recruitment process in the context of talent management	The recruitment process with criteria based on manpower planning has not yet been oriented to talent
		The recruitment process is prioritized to close the personnel vacancy for all superior personnel
		Talent mapping for each position has not been fully carried out
		It takes time and process to build optimal talent for personnel
		Recruitment is adjusted to open positions to be filled with confirmatory tests to detect personnel talents
5	The human resources status in recruitment	Status of singles for fresh graduates and sought a single for regular recruitment
		Eliminating the culture of seniority requires process and time
		Old age personnel are still defensive for talent development
		Assessment of key performance indicators for internal promotion
		Carry out a limited personnel engagement survey
6	The human resources training and development process	Development results in standardized HR grades and classes requiring training process
		Training need analysis is needed to find out the learning need analysis directed at developing the talent of personnel
		Human capital audits are needed by external successors as a recommendation for personnel development
		Structural or functional training based on passion is directed at developing structural or functional talents
7	The human resources training and development targets	On the job training becomes a need not to disturb the work process
		Future leadership development program through e-learning training for certain employees
		Targeting talent pool through e-learning training for all employees
		Provide specialized talent management training in stages due to the large number of employees
8	The human resources placement process in the context of talent	Has not consistently placed personnel with talent pool based on talent management
		Placement using the results of existing personnel assessment according to the manpower plan
		Have not use KPIs as an intensive use other than at the Central Office

	management	There is no talent management for functional positions
		The relatively long administrative and bureaucratic process requirements are still used in the talent pool for structural positions
9	Implementation of talent pool activities	Talent pool activities are coordinated with limited e-learning in certain areas.
		Implementation of talent pool through an assessment center that is equipped with internal and external assessors
		Human capital portfolio mapping is done through personnel assessment
		The limitations of the course of talent management in the career path of personnel
10	Process of assessment n recruitment results and training in human resources placement	There is still subjectivity in evaluating recruitment results in placement
		The results of recruitment are not too related to placement because placement is determined by need
		The process of evaluating recruitment results and training results is used for human capital improvement by stakeholders
		Evaluation of training results should be directly related to aggressive growth performance to increase brand awareness after training
11	Human resources recruitment systems	Human capital achievements support the transformation from companies to business entities.
		Recruitment requires a foundation for inspiring corporate culture that is supported by rotation and mutation of positions synchronized with the training that is followed
		The challenge of learning centers is for the development of potential talent of personnel who need innovation in human capital practice
		Personnel development is adjusted to the potential of talent possessed by personnel to increase the freshness of personnel at work
		There is the potential for millennial employees to become potential talents to fill the various required job descriptions.
12	The human resources retirement preparation program.	Provide skills training during retirement preparation to remain productive.
		Retired employees can be used for assessor positions because of their experience
		Prepare an old age program from special teams and e-learning teams
		Planning a program to be mentally prepared after retirement becomes a personal choice

Overall conditions that reflect the implementation of the talent management program rolled out by the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 as mentioned above are the conditions found in the implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018. Each of the conditions for the implementation of the talent management program initiated by BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 has an unsupportive and supportive impact of the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

Impacts that do not support the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 are undesirable impacts of the conditions for implementing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. Impacts that support the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 are the desired impacts of the

conditions implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

Impacts that do not support or impacts that support the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 are conditions formed by the causes of the impact of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. Using the above reference, the results of the discussion on the implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018, as follows:

Table 4.3: Discussion Result - The Implementation of Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018

Nu	The Condition for the implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018	Impact of the Conditions for the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018	Causes of the Impact of the Conditions for the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018
1	Changes in organizational structure due to the transformation of the law, service excellence oriented, changes in the business environment	Support the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program	Organizational structures that accommodate the talents of personnel can produce intent changes in structure.
2	Changes in organizational culture are still in process, requiring changes in profile competency, changing cultural values at work	Does not support the successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program	Changes in the value of culture in working to produce the desired organizational culture talent management is difficult to do through a fast process by all employees.
3 u. 53	Pre Memory	Pre Memory	Pre Memory

The results of the discussion of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 shown in the above table are only part of the entire table that cannot be displayed due to limited display space.

Based on the above table and by focusing on the impact of the conditions of the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018, it can be stated that the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program from 2014 to 2018 produces unsupportive and supportive impacts of the successful implementation of the talent management program rolled out by the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018. Impacts that do not support the successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 each are changes in organizational culture that is still in process, which requires changes in profile competency and changes in cultural values at work, while impacts that support the successful implementation of talent programs management that was rolled out by BPJS

Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 was a change in organizational structure due to the transformation of the law and changes in the business environment.

By taking into account the overall results of the discussion on the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018, it is known that the impacts that did not support the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 talent management program include changes in organizational culture and processes that require changes in profile competency and changes in cultural values at work, the process of structural change requires the process of transformation of employees into human capital, talent mapping for each position has not been fully carried out, it takes time and process to build optimal personnel talent, training need analysis is needed to find out the learning need analysis directed at developing talent, and has not consistently placed personnel with a talent pool based on talent management.

4.2 Constraints in the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018

By taking into account the conditions for the implementation of the talent management program the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018, it is seen that there are conditions that reflect constraints in the implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018. Based on the data collected and reduced, the results of research on the constraints in the implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018, are as follows.

Table 4.4: Research Results - Constraints in the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018

Nu.	Coding Topics	Constraints in the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018
1	Structural changes and organizational culture changes	Changes in organizational culture are still in process, requiring changes in profile competency, changing cultural values at work The process of culture change requires the support of all employees, requiring the acceleration of the process in accordance with the intended milestone. The process of structural change requires the process of transforming employees into human capital
2	Reasons for using human capital	----
3	The use of the term talent management	----
4 u. 12	Pre Memory	Pre Memory

The results of research on the constraints in implementing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 shown in Table 4.4. The table is only part of the entire table that cannot be displayed due to limited display space.

Constraints encountered in the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 as seen above, basically is the condition of the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 which does not support the successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. Each constrain in the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 has a large obstacle or a small obstacle to the successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

Constraints that have a large obstacle are obstacles that require adequate solutions to get the successful implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018. Constraints that have a small inhibition are obstacles that only require simple solutions to get successful implementation of the talent management program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018.

Constraints that have a large inhibitory or have a small inhibitory are basically conditions that are determined by the causes of the inhibition of constraints to get successful implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. By using these references, the results of the discussion about the constraints faced in the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 are as follows.

Table 4.5: Discussion Results - Constraints in the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018

Nu.	Constraints in the Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018	Impediment of Constraints to Getting Successful Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018	Causes of Impediment from Constraints to Getting Successful Implementation of the Talent Management Program BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018
1	Changes in organizational culture are still in process, requiring changes in profile competency, changing cultural values at work	Great inhibition towards the successful implementation of the talent management program	The process of organizational culture change has complications for changes in personnel culture
2	The process of culture change requires the support of all employees, requiring the acceleration of the process in accordance with the intended milestone.	Great inhibition towards the successful implementation of the talent management program	Heterogeneity of personnel hinders the process of organizational culture change supporting talent management
3 u. 8	Pre Memory	Pre Memory	Pre Memory
9	Carry out a limited personnel engagement survey	Small inhibition towards the successful implementation of the talent management program	It will be very useful if the engagement survey is extended to all personnel.

10 u. 53	Pre Memory	Pre Memory	Pre Memory
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The results of the discussion about the constraints in implementing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 shown in Table 4.5. The table is only part of the entire table that cannot be displayed due to limited display space.

Based on the table above and by focusing on the obstacles of constraints to get successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 talent management program, it can be stated that the constraints in the implementation of the talent management program the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 consist of constraints with large impediments or constraints with small impediments. The constraints with great impediments to achieve successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 is that organizational culture changes are still in process that requires a change in profile competency and changes in cultural values at work, the process of cultural change requires the support of all employees who want to accelerate the process in accordance with the intended milestone. Whereas the obstacle with little inhibition to get the successful implementation of the talent management program that was rolled out by the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 was to conduct a limited personnel engagement survey.

By taking into account the overall results of the discussion of constraints in the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018, it is known that the constraints with great impediments to get the successful implementation of the talent management program the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 2014-2018 are changes in organizational culture still in process that requires changes in profile competency and make changes in cultural values at work, the process of culture change need the support of all employees who want to accelerate the process in accordance with the intended milestone, the process of culture change needs the support of all employees, the process of transforming employees into human capital, takes time and process to build personnel talent the optimal, as well as the limitations of the implementation of talent management in the career path of personnel.

4.3 The Roadmap for Developing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Talent Management Program in Supporting the Success of the Organization

The roadmap for developing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program in supporting the success of the organization as a road map is an effort to be made to support the success of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan organization. It means that the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program has a direct link with the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 and also the constraints faced in implementing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

Since all constraints faced in the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 are an inseparable part of the implementation of BPJS

Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018, the direct linkage of the roadmap for developing talent management programs is focused on the conditions of the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. Based on the data collected and has been reduced, the results of research on the foundation roadmap for BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program development are as follows.

Table 4.6: Research Result - The Basics of the Roadmap for Talent Management Program Development BPJS Ketenagakerjaan

No	Coding Topics	The Basics of the Roadmap for Talent Management Program Development BPJS Ketenagakerjaan
1	Structural changes and organizational culture changes	Changes in organizational structure due to the transformation of the law, service excellence oriented, changes in the business environment
		Changes in organizational culture are still in process, requiring changes in profile competency, changing cultural values at work
		The process of culture change requires the support of all employees, requiring the acceleration of the process in accordance with the intended milestone.
		The process of structural change requires initiation through strategic planning, is expected to increase the number of BPJS Employment, change the Board of Commissioners to the Supervisory Board.
		The process of structural change requires the process of transforming employees into human capital
2 u. 12	Pre Memory	Pre Memory

The results of the research on the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program shown in Table 4.6. The table is only a part of the entire table that cannot be displayed due to limited display space.

The overall basis of the roadmap for BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program development as mentioned above is a condition that is taken into consideration in the preparation of the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program, which will be used for the future. The foundation of the roadmap for the development of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program for the future, which takes into account the priority of the problem and the weighting of the rank of the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 is transformed as a roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program, in part as shown below.

Table 4.7: Discussion Result - Roadmap for
 Talent Management Program Development BPJS Ketenagakerjaan

No	Basics of Roadmap for Talent Management Program Development BPJS Ketenagakerjaan	Problem Priority	Problem Weight Rating	Roadmap for Talent Management Program Development BPJS Ketenagakerjaan
1	Changes in organizational structure due to the transformation of the law, service excellence oriented, changes in the business environment	Problems that are very urgent, serious and important enough to develop		1.1. Measured service excellence improvement based on key performance indicators by all structural and functional officials
2	Changes in organizational culture are still in process, requiring changes in profile competency, changing cultural values at work			1.2. Accelerating the process of organizational culture change through changes in work culture by each personnel
3	The process of culture change requires the support of all employees, requiring the acceleration of the process in accordance with the intended milestone.			1.3. The acceleration of the formation of organizational culture through talented personnel that changes the work culture of personnel
4	The process of structural change requires initiation through strategic planning, is expected to increase the number of BPJS Employment, change the Board of Commissioners to the Supervisory Board.			1.4. Strengthening strategic plans through comprehensive and applicable strategic planning.
5	The process of structural change requires the process of transforming employees into human capital			1.5. Transforming organizational structures into multi-functional structures.
6 u. 53	Pre Memory			Pre Memory

The results of the discussion on the roadmap for the development of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program shown in Table 4.7. The table is only part of the entire table which cannot be displayed due to limited display space.

By taking into account the results of the analysis above, it can be stated that the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program is the result of an analysis of the implementation conditions of the 2014-2018 BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program as a basics and taking into account the priority of the problem and determine the weight of the ranks of the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

Taking into account the overall results of the discussion, the roadmap for the development of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program are:

1. Changes in the structure and acceleration of the process of organizational culture change.

1.1. Measured service excellence improvement based on key performance indicators by all structural and functional officials.

1.2. Accelerating the process of organizational culture change through changes in work culture by each personnel.

1.3. The acceleration of the formation of organizational culture through talented personnel that changes the work culture of personnel.

1.4. Strengthening strategic plans through comprehensive and applicable strategic planning.

1.5. Transforming organizational structures into multi-functional structures.

2. The widespread implementation of talent management.

2.1. Increased understanding of personnel about the talent for self-development as an executive of the organization.

2.2. Planning and the process of growing the talent of personnel carried out by a sustainable organization.

2.3. Increased understanding of personnel about talent for personnel who are sincere, productive and contributory to organization.

2.4. Increased understanding of leadership elements regarding the task of building and developing personnel talents.

3. Targeted training and human resource development.

3.1. Prepare basic modules for developing talent distributed to all employees.

3.2. Prepare special talent development modules for all task areas in the organization.

3.3. Carry out talents pool through e-learning training for all employees

3.4. Carry out talents training for all grade levels of employees.

4. The process of evaluating the results of recruitment and training in the placement of human resources.

4.1. Increased objectivity in evaluating recruitment results in personnel placement.

4.2. Conduct personnel placement based on recruitment results and personnel talents.

4.3. Development of the meaning of human capital by all personnel in the organization.

4.4. Use of performance appraisals based on periodic training results.

5. Human resource recruitment system.

5.1. Increased understanding that the achievement of human capital is a synergistic achievement of all elements of the leadership.

5.2. Transform talented people as organizational culture values.

5.3. Preparation of an innovation framework for human capital practice by organizational learning centers.

5.4. The development of personnel that inclusively considers talent development.

5.5. Development of potential talent for millennial personnel.

6. The meaning of functional human capital.

- 6.1. Improved understanding of organizational transformation through the interpretation of human capital by all elements of the leadership.
- 6.2. Increasing the meaning of human capital in achieving organizational goals and success.
- 6.3. Improvement of personnel management through awareness of personnel as organizational resources and tools.
- 6.4. Increased understanding of personnel to be productive in outlining the vision and mission of the organization.
7. Implementation of the recruitment process with talent management direction.
 - 7.1. Intensive use of personnel talent criteria in the recruitment process.
 - 7.2. Use of talent criteria for determining leading personnel.
 - 7.3. Perform mapping based on the talents of each position in the organization.
 - 7.4. Accelerating the development of personnel talent for all positions in the organization.
 - 7.5. Detection of personnel talent is prioritized in personnel recruitment.
8. The process of training and developing human resources.
 - 8.1. Standardize talent at a minimum for each grade level and class of employees.
 - 8.2. Directly link training need analysis with personnel talent development.
 - 8.3. Regular use of external successors in carrying out human capital audits.
 - 8.4. Enhance material for developing talent for personnel in the training of structural officials and officials functional.
9. The process of placing human resources with the direction of talent management.
 - 9.1. Increased consistency in personnel placement based on talent pool.
 - 9.2. Increasing the use of assessment results in developing personnel talents.
 - 9.3. Intensifying the use of KPIs in all branches and work units.
 - 9.4. Talent management planning for functional positions.
 - 9.5. Implementing talent pool that minimizes administrative and bureaucratization requirements.
10. Utilization of the status of human resources in recruitment.
 - 10.1. Utilization of personnel who have work experience as a driver of personnel change talent.
 - 10.2. Use of key performance indicators to measure the development of personnel talent.
 - 10.3. Conducting personnel engagement surveys in all work units.
11. Implementation of talent pool activities.
 - 11.1. Implementation of the talent pool with e-learning in all work units.
 - 11.2. Utilization of internal assessors and external assessors in conducting talent assessments in the talent pool.
 - 11.3. Use of personnel assessments to detect personnel talent development.
 - 11.4. Directly linking personnel talents in the career path of personnel.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

5.1 Conclusion

- 1) The implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 resulted in unsupportive and supportive impacts of the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018. Impacts that did not support the successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 included changes in organizational culture. process that requires changes in profile competency and changes in cultural values at work, the process of changing the structure requires the process of transformation of employees into human capital, talent mapping for each position has not been fully carried out, it takes time and process to build optimal personnel talent, training need analysis needed to know the learning need analysis that is directed at developing talent, and has not consistently placed personnel with talent pool based on talent management.
- 2) Constraints in the implementation of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 consist of constraints with large obstacles or constraints with small obstacles. Constraints with great obstacles to achieve successful implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 include the process of cultural change that requires the support of all employees, requires the process of transforming employees into human capital, takes time and process to build optimal personnel talent, and limitations the implementation of talent management in the career path of personnel.
- 3) The roadmap for developing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program is the result of an analysis of the implementation conditions of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 as a foundation and taking into account the priority problems and weighting of the rank of the problems of implementing the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018.

5.2 Suggestion

- 1) It is suggested to the leadership of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan to consider the development of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program through the roadmap for developing BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program as previously shown.
- 2) By taking into account the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 and for the successful development of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program, it is recommended that the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan leadership 1) consider transforming human capital as *kapital insani* 2) consider transforming human resource management by calling as *sumber daya insani* management.

- 3) By taking into account the obstacles in the implementation of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program 2014-2018 and the successful development of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan talent management program, it is recommended that the leadership of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan 1) make talent management an integral part of the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Strategic Plan and 2) prepare measurement of talent development programs. personnel through key performance indicators for each position in the BPJS Ketenagakerjaan organization.

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